

DIAGNOSIS OF KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS AND QUALIFICATIONS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article is about the diagnosis of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, its significance, its impact on the educational process, in what order to conduct and use the results.*

Keywords: *diagnostic assessment, educational strategies, self-assessment, improvement of educational results, individual education.*

One of the tools that stands out for its ability to control the direction of education in a clear and understandable way is diagnostic evaluation. This initial assessment tool is not just a measure of knowledge - it is a compass that teachers use to control students' concepts and skills before starting new classes. Diagnosis is a way for teachers to understand what their students know, what they don't know, and how they learn better. This concept is invaluable because it allows teachers to adapt their teaching strategies to meet individual educational needs.

Diagnostic assessment is usually characterized by the ability of students to identify previous knowledge and skills, their ability to identify educational deficiencies, and their role in informing future education. Research shows that the goal of inquiry is to identify the strengths of individual students and, most importantly, the weaknesses of qualities that the student has not yet fully mastered. The purpose of diagnostic assessment is not to place assessments on students or to measure their performance in relation to others. Instead, the purpose of diagnostic evaluation is to understand each student as an individual learner. Using diagnostic evaluation, teachers can make sure that each student receives the necessary support at the right time. This makes learning more effective and interesting and helps students realize their full potential.

Diagnostic assessments are not the only solution. Diagnosis can take different forms, each serving a specific purpose and giving different concepts about the learning process. There are three common species:

1. Pre-tests. They are given before a new section or class to assess what students know about the subject. They help teachers understand where to start their studies and which areas to focus more on.

2. Self-assessment. These allow students to evaluate their concepts and skills. They can be a powerful tool for developing responsibility in self-awareness and learning.

3. Teacher's observations. Teachers monitor students during classes to assess their abilities and understanding. These observations can provide valuable insights into student learning processes and behaviors. The effective implementation of a diagnostic assessment requires a well-thought-out approach. This is not only to choose the right assessment or interpret the results correctly, but also to use this information to inform education and support student learning.

Some features of diagnostic evaluation:

Low rates: diagnostic evaluation is usually not used for evaluation. Pre-evaluation: diagnostic evaluation is often used before a new section or course.

Identifying educational deficiencies: diagnostic evaluation helps to determine what students know and what they need to learn.

Manual instruction: diagnostic assessment helps teachers adapt their instructions to meet the needs of their students.

Encouraging grouping: diagnostic evaluation helps teachers group students to enrich or correct them.

Basic level setting: diagnostic assessments help set the base for students to learn during a department or course.

Some examples of diagnostic assessment include: pre-unit tests, individualized assessments, and reading diagnostic assessments. Teachers can also use questionnaires to get a general idea of student knowledge. Here are some strategies to master diagnostic evaluation:

1. Start with specific learning goals: before evaluating what students know, you need to know what you want them to learn. Having specific learning goals will help you choose a diagnostic assessment and help you interpret the results.

2. Choose the right assessment for your goals and context: different types of diagnostic assessment are suitable for different purposes and contexts. When choosing an assessment, take into account your learning goals, your students and your teaching context.

3. Use the results to provide guidance: diagnostic assessments are only as useful as the actions they express. Use the results to control your instructions and help students where they need them the most.

4. Involving students in the process: diagnostic evaluation can be a tool for developing self-awareness and responsibility in students. Involve them in the process, help them understand their strengths and areas of improvement.

5. Review and adjustment: diagnostic evaluation is a continuous process. Review the results regularly, change your instructions as needed, and reassess to track progress.

In summary, the real power of diagnostic evaluation is beyond the information they provide; it depends on how teachers use this information to change teaching and learning. These assessments serve as compasses and guide a more efficient and personalized learning experience for each student. The concepts accumulated as a result of diagnostic assessments make it possible to comprehend the strengths, weaknesses and previous knowledge of students in every possible way. Teachers armed with this knowledge can make informed educational decisions by adapting their approaches to meet the specific needs of each student. By recognizing individual learning styles, preferences, and training levels, teachers can create a learning environment that encourages activity, motivation, and growth.

In education, it is important to know where students stand on their educational path. Diagnostic assessment is a reliable tool, providing teachers with insights into student strengths and areas of improvement. Here we will learn the basics of diagnostic assessment, study its purpose, components, advantages, difficulties and the best practices of its introduction in online education. While diagnostic assessments are primarily used to identify deficiencies in knowledge before the start of the learning process, teachers can also use the same assessment at the end of the learning period to assess the learning process of students and determine the effectiveness of teaching methods.

By analyzing the results of diagnostic assessments, teachers can effectively direct the planning of their lessons to eliminate certain educational shortcomings or misconceptions in the

learning process. Diagnostic assessment helps teachers adapt to common problems, such as the individual needs of students. By conducting an effective diagnostic assessment at the beginning of the training period, teachers can accurately individualize their instructions, depending on the level of development of each student. By definition, diagnostic evaluation is often carried out at the beginning of the training period. By performing the same assessment after training or in the middle, teachers can monitor student progress and assess the effectiveness of teaching strategies.

This method allows teachers to adapt their teaching methods to ensure that students' learning outcomes are continuously increased. In addition, the results of the initial diagnostic assessment serve as a reliable criterion for comparing the current level of training during the training process.

Conclusion

Diagnostic assessment serves as an important element of the learning process and provides invaluable insights into students' strengths, weaknesses, and individual educational needs. By identifying deficiencies in knowledge prior to the start of education, teachers can adapt their teaching strategies to improve educational outcomes. While there are challenges, adherence to advanced experiences ensures effective diagnostic evaluation, guiding teachers towards goals to help a meaningful and impact learning experience for all students.

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